

xRAGE Against the Machines

Preparing an Old Code for an Onslaught of New Platforms

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Background: The xRAGE Code

- xRAGE is an Eulerian AMR radiation-hydrodynamics code
- Descended from code originally written c.1990
- Contains $O(500K)$ lines source code
 - Not counting numerous third-party libraries, from LANL and elsewhere
- Mostly Fortran, some C and C++
- Historically MPI-only parallelism, starting to introduce Kokkos

xRAGE applications: asteroid impact in ocean,
ICF capsule implosion

Background: The Machines

- **2015: Trinity** – Intel Xeon Phi many-core
- **2018: Sierra** – IBM P9 + NVIDIA V100
- **2023: Crossroads** – Intel SPR + high-bandwidth memory
- **2024: Venado** – NVIDIA GH200
- **2024-5?: El Capitan** – AMD MI300A

*5 major new platforms in 10 years
with 3 in ~18 months!*

The need for modernizing xRAGE

As of 2013, 20+ years of high-pressure work had left xRAGE with significant technical debt. This made it difficult to:

- understand the code flow or data flow
- maintain the code
- add new features
- *train new developers as older staff retire*
- *refactor for advanced architectures, such as Trinity, Sierra, . . .*
- These factors (especially the last two) made us realize that things needed to change!

Trinity and Sierra

Refactoring the code

- At the start, any file could use data or call routines from any other file
- Working hard over ~15 months, did a major code refactor *in place*
- Separated code into well-defined packages
- This enabled other changes *on a per-package basis*
 - Unit testing, documentation
 - Code cleanup
 - Performance optimization
 - Physics improvements
 - Advanced architecture support

xRAGE dependency graphs,
before and after refactoring

Improving the test system

- Before refactor started, our regression test suite wasn't well maintained
- During refactor, team made more effort to keep tests passing ("wall of green")
- Started with integrated tests, added unit tests as we refactored
- Later, added continuous integration through GitLab-CI

CROSS PLATFORM RESULTS (Notes)			
	CI	MC	TFI
intel	intel	intel	
default	ppermpp	default	
Totals	147/147	147/147	146/148
merge			
RunTime	13234	15270	6725
Test			
AMR dart	Pass 239	Pass 189	Pass 109
AMR ubast	Pass 187	Pass 230	Pass 111
AMR sod	Pass 26	Pass 66	Pass 19
Anisofat3breth	Pass 74	Pass 410	Pass 81
Cond	Pass 12	Pass 22	Pass 9
CrushAlum	Pass 99	Pass 110	Pass 66
CrushRP	Pass 76	Pass 48	Pass 26
Exact_Cond1dLin	Pass 9	Pass 10	Pass 5
Exact_Cond2dLin	Pass 138	Pass 100	Pass 67
Exact_Cond3dLin	Pass 140	Pass 101	Pass 56
HE_AIR	Pass 70	Pass 109	Pass 41
HE_CorroGrande	Pass 35	Pass 35	Pass 21
HE_FF	Pass 11	Pass 12	Pass 8
HE_FFPB	Pass 237	Pass 162	Pass 113
HE_FF_RS	Pass 23	Pass 35	Pass 18
HE_IJ	Pass 22	Pass 28	Pass 15
HE_FB	Pass 15	Pass 30	Pass 13
HE_SURF	Pass 231	Pass 246	Pass 121
HE_SURFmerge	Pass 13	Pass 15	Pass 10
HE_SURFplus	Pass 203	Pass 191	Pass 110
HE_SURFplusZND	Pass 46	Pass 33	Pass 32

Nightly test report, Gitlab CI report

Adding GPU support

- First attempt: Tried to build our own Kokkos-like system in Fortran
 - Fortran doesn't have templates, lambdas
 - Became too difficult to maintain, expand
- Second attempt: OpenMP offloading
 - Compatible with Fortran
 - Offload implementations weren't mature
 - Didn't handle F2003 derived types
- Third attempt: C++ and Kokkos
 - Requires Fortran -> C++ port
 - Flexible, well-supported
 - Can convert incrementally, do a small set of high-value routines first

NVIDIA GH200, AMD MI300 GPUs

Building a bridge from Fortran to C++ and Kokkos

- Uses Fortran interop features from 2003, 2018 standards
 - `CFI_cdesc_t` type allows C/C++ to access a Fortran “dope vector”
 - `Kokkos::View` can be built using pointer to data, dope vector metadata
- Builds interoperable Fortran and C++ arrays from a single description, using:
 - auto-generated code
 - template metaprogramming
- Allows our main Fortran code to call Kokkos kernels on GPUs!

Adopting new tools

- Confluence wiki for documentation
- GitLab for version control and CI
 - Learned merge request workflow
 - Took some developer education
- Spack package manager
- CMake build system generator
 - Replaced home-grown system
 - Took quite a while to replicate the complex behavior of our home-grown system

Changing the software culture

Computer scientists and RSEs have different culture, priorities than domain scientists

We learned to communicate...

- Added a CS lead to the project
- Added more support for CS, RSE project staff
- Allocated time for domain scientists to do code cleanup/quality work

Summary

- We've made a lot of progress in the past 10+ years
- Because of this, we're better prepared to move to the new, unusual platforms that are coming in...

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Questions? Discussion?

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